

Accounting and Finance Teaching Enjoyment & Pedagogy for Quality Enhancements, Establishments and Empowerments

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Abstract

Teachers are the facilitators for the accounting and finance students. To facilitate, they should share the practical and theoretical knowledge, what they acquired during their education and experiences. Students must enjoy the teaching. Learn to Teach and Teach to Learn should be the motto of accounting and finance teachers. Accounting and Finance Education must be focused to the subjects for which the pedagogy must be adopted using chalk & talk, audio, videos, games, assignments, surprise quizzes, case studies, research projects, group discussions, seminar presentations, guest lectures, workshops, written exams on computer, evaluations through the software, industrial visits, good communication skills, infrastructures of the classroom, digital libraries, laptops with internet connection, monitoring and scrutinizing, transparency, 360 degree evaluation and eagle eyes are very important to promote the stream which help to improve and sustain the subjects also to the real economy development with proper discipline system in Ethiopia.

Keywords: Enjoy Teaching; Teaching Pedagogy and Teacher's quality.

Introduction

The teaching profession is the happiest profession. To excel in the profession, teachers should be the master in their profession. It is Nobel profession. They promote the future for the society, and develop teaching pedagogy. They should know what is teaching? Why teaching? And what is the necessity of teaching? Teachers are the facilitators for the students. To facilitate, they should share the knowledge, what they acquired. Students must enjoy the teaching. Learn to Teach and Teach to Learn should be the motto of teachers. (Bennett, N. and Carré, C.(eds.),1993) "For effective transfer of knowledge the students must enjoy the teaching" only when the faculty enjoy the teaching, the students will enjoy their teachings. For this teachers should spend a lot of time for learning theoretically and practically in accounting and finance. (Bennett, N. and Turner-Bissett, R., 1993).

Background and Overview

Teachers occupy an enviable position in society. Teachers are responsible for so many things. They commence high societal regards even today. People who have chosen teaching career, they should work for themselves, to their students, to their institution and to the society (Darling-Hammond, L. and Bransford, J. (Eds.), 2005). They should watch all of their words carefully when they speak to the students. Teachers should be a role model for the students. They should spend more time with the students and for preparations. To improve one's teaching ability, it is essential that continuous assessment and evaluation of the class is necessary. Good and enjoyable teaching In this context, evaluation always improve the teaching quality. The effort of the teachers result in deep personal satisfaction and professional success. Such practices add up over the period of time and ensure them life long career of "enjoyable teaching". Competition in other hand, is the reason for stress, strain and tension of the teachers. To face the competition, lot of preparation, is needed. Enjoy Teaching Learn to teach and teach to learn. The teaching is in learning domain. By touch we can learn, by sight we can learn, by experience and experiment we can learn. Learning is unlimited. Teaching should be thought of helping

students. For which, i. Foster a good learning atmosphere, ii. Manage the uninterested students into interested iii. Create good environment in the class iv. Be serious without creating excessive tension v. Be prepared – i.e. have a flexible teaching plan in the mind look for teachable movement vi. Be positive towards the learners vii. Be confident viii. Plan and practice the lectures ix. State what should be learned x. Use effective teaching techniques xi. Situate the topic in the bigger picture xii. Provide adequate contents of the modules xiii. Giving introduction of the session and modules xiiii. Involve learners in to the process - For example present the problem and respond the questions xv. Summarize the findings and discussion xvi. Do research and prepare report xvii. Use questions effectively xviii. Summarize the take home points at the end of the discussion (M. Moses Antony Rajendran, 2012), To use the follow up research and report to the group as an inquisitive exercise rather than a punitive exercise. The following methods will help students to learn well. Common test methods, lectures with discussion, brain storming, videos tapes, class discussion and small group discussion. The case study, role playing, report back session ,guest speakers ,panel of experts and value clarification exercises would help to educate the students well. Seven Principles of Good Teaching Practices.

- a. Encouraging contact between students and faculty
- b. Developing reciprocity and co-operation among students
- c. Encouraging active learning
- d. Giving prompt feed back
- e. Emphasizing time on task
- f. Communicating with high expectations
- g. Respecting diverse talents and ways of learning.

Evaluation of Enhancement Good evaluations is like doing good research. In both cases, teachers are trying to answer some important questions about an important topic.

Important question in the assessment of teaching methods are:

- How good and effective is my teaching?
- What are the areas in which I have to improve ?
- What are the areas in which I am very good at?

Sometimes to evaluate our own teaching effectively. The methods of effective evaluation of own teaching.

Techniques of evaluation

- Self-monitoring
- Audio/video tape
- Information from students
- Questionnaire
- Interviews
- Student test results

Outside Observers:

- Fellow Faculty Members
- Senior Faculty Members
- External Professional Assistance

Effective Teaching

To do this, presentation skills,, visual aids for teaching, communications, body language, lesson planning and time management are very much important. To reach out every student, ensure equality and motivate the low motivated students.

Motivating Students

Most of the students expect their instructors to inspire, challenge and stimulate them. The effective learning of the students in the class room depend on teachers ability to maintain the interest. This interest bring the students first place in their course.

Accounting and Finance

As we are all know that accounting is the language of the finance. It is important of buying and selling of goods and services. To do commerce the knowledge of accounting, finance, marketing, management, corporate laws, information technology, business mathematics and statistics, business communication, accounting ethics and auditing are very

important. To teach these subjects to the students teacher must understand the theoretical concepts and technical skill is must. In this global village every thing is business. They are trading and non trading sectors. To do the business the accounting and finance knowledge is very important which helps to show the profit or loss of the business, doing it ethically, etc.

Pedagogy in Accounting and Finance

Accounting and Finance Education must be focused to the relevant subjects for which the pedagogy must be adopted using chalk & talk, audio, videos, games, assignments, surprise quizzes, case studies, research projects, group discussions, seminar presentations, guest lectures, workshops, written exams on computer, evaluations through the software, industrial visits, good communication skills, infrastructures of the classroom, digital libraries, laptops with internet connection, monitoring and scrutinizing, transparency, 360 degree evaluation and eagle eyes are very important to promote the stream which help to improve and sustain the subjects also to the real the economy development with proper discipline system in the country.

Teaching as Profession in Accounting and Finance

As we know that teaching profession is one of the happiest profession. To excel in the profession, teachers should be the master in the field. They promote the future for the society in accounting and finance, and develop teaching pedagogy. They should know what is teaching? Why teaching? And what is the necessity of teaching? Teachers are the facilitators for the students. To facilitate, they should share the knowledge, what they acquired from the commerce stream. Learn to Teach and Teach to Learn should be the moto of teachers. "For effective transfer of knowledge the students must enjoy the teaching" only when the faculty enjoy the teaching, the students will enjoy their teachings. For this teachers should spend a lot of time for learning and doing research in the field of the subject. Teacher should posses good commanding communication skills; adopting methodology of teaching using ppts, videos, assignment, case study, surprise quiz, research project, group discussion, seminar presentation, guest lectures, workshop and written exams;

Active team member is a one who effectively collaborates with all levels of staff members and establishes quality relationship with students. In the millennium years the assignment, the teaching subject should be in audio and video forms like movies. This will catch the students and minimize the work of the teachers. So teachers can more involve in evaluation and research. The teaching is always in learning domain. By touch, by sight, by experiencing and experimenting anybody can learn Learning is unlimited. Teaching also should be thought of helping students. (M. Moses Antony Rajendran, 2012).

Curriculum

The new curriculum which creates new job openings. For the new curriculum fresh and also experienced faculty members need 'faculty development and training program's trained by experienced and ethical teaches. The curriculum committee always consult the industries to update the curriculums. This will help the students to get an employment opportunity in the national and global job market. (Nespor, J., 1987)

Important of the Accounting and Finance Education

Accounting and Finance Education should allow the students to reach their fullest potential in terms of cognitive, emotional and creative capacities. Increasing mobility has also brought concerns about the extent to which learning, measured in terms of qualifications, is transferable. This has led to increased monitoring and regulation of education systems and to a flourishing industry of cross-national learning assessment using comparative benchmarks. When thinking about the quality of education it is useful to distinguish between educational outcomes and the processes leading to pupils. The ideas that human nature is essentially good, that individual behavior is autonomous (within the constraints of heredity and environment), that everyone is unique, that all people are born equal and subsequent inequality is a product of circumstance and that reality for each person is defined by himself or herself characterize a range of liberal humanist philosophers from Locke to Rousseau. In India, the first President Dr. S. Radhakrishnan already insisted on Quality Education in 1947.

Factors involved in Quality Education

- **Discipline, Decorum, Dignity and Decency,**
- **Infrastructure Facilities,**
- **Human Rights Education**
- **Academic : Lecture System, Syllabus System, Examination System and New Education**
- **Copy Right and Pattern Right**
- **Smartness**
- **Custom and Tradition**
- **Politics**

- **Communication**
- **Physical Education**
- **Personality Development**
- **Ethics**
- **Spiritual**

Academic Approach

In the quality education academic approach is very important. In this millennium there is a need for an in-depth academic knowledge with a good grounding in one's subject. University degrees alone will not fulfill the requirements of today's quality education. Proficiency in subject and additional skills are in great demand. The following points are involving in to improve the Academic Area.

Lecture System Definition:

Creative expression of inner spiritual lectures or lecture is a living vibration, it is ideal for any educational system or an indispensable place. Again, lecture conversation has an important place in education System. Lectures are indispensable in the educational system.

In addition, lectures are useful in (a) the introduction of the subject, (b) to stimulate interest in the theme of the great cause, and (iii) propose a panoramic view of the subject, (4) to interpret the general difficulties or obstacles, which is usually faced by a large number of students in their studies, (v) establishing good atmosphere for some pervasive and (f) to initiate a rapid and massive training program. Finally, the report talks as research work has its undeniable position and value. However, in the above-mentioned if the objectives or conditions are absent, speech becomes dry, boring, ineffective, regardless of the interests of students, therefore meaningless, which has to be changed radically.

Syllabus System

A syllabus, not only gives an over – all view of a subject but also serves as an instrument in attaining certain goals. As such, it presents to the students the overall contents of the subject which he is going to learn by invoking a interest and creating a learning attitude on the subject. But uniformity of syllabus may cut down the innate tendencies of curiosity, variation, digression & spontaneity. At the same time, pertaining strictly to the prescribed syllabus alone is a wrong approach. Since knowledge is expansive, subject-related studies in the light of current scenario should be encouraged.

In the actual operation of the educational process, these has to be an 'evolutionary syllabi' catering to the inner growth of the student and the societal needs to make it into a harmonious whole. The ultimate result should be spontaneous progress & perfection evolving an all-rounded personality. Progress of the student is linked with motivation, which in turn is connected with curiosity. It is so because, only curiosity can lead to a serious search after Truth. Such a transformation emanating the truth by means of rigorous training masks a real progress. Physical and mental growth should go hand-in-hand. Unfortunately, it's not so in many cases. Therefore, while introducing a programme, a competency test can be conducted to assess the psychological level of the student. So that, the programme can be suitably modified or can be modified to suit their needs of growth. In this context, the role of a teacher is to guide, counsel and help the student in choosing a programmed by highlighting its merits and progressive paths rather than imposing it. Every program of study must be a combination of traditional and technical components, in other words, a preparatory ground for their vocation. A well-framed syllabus should maintain the balance between knowledge and skill. New Education must make room for spiritual sustenance as well. On the whole, syllabus system should take into account the physical, mental, moral & spiritual growth of the student to bring in harmony. Examination System Test/Exams as a means of judging achievement plays an important role in any ideal system of education.

It helps in stimulation, self-evaluation and throws light on the actual capacity of performance of a student. But the tests can be of varied types to analyze the different skills in a person – For instance, in order to assess the competency of a student in a particular language, a test can be conducted on four levels such as, listening , speaking, reading and writing. In case of vocational programmers, a test at the end of a training period justifies the programmed. Written tests alone cannot serve the purpose of judging achievements as it faces the risk of memorizing the reproducing the subject. Whereas, the sole purpose of tests is to provide a way to students to think and generate new ideas with clarity and precision.

Therefore, tests or exams must pave way for a health competition among students by boosting their self-confidence and growth. Test occupy only marginal place in the total system of education. Every country with its own rich tradition and cultural heritage must inculcate values in students by means of telling them stories, folktales, parables, in daily conversations and also by stimulating their curiosity with striking ideas, discussions and assigning projects. Education should be value- based. It must chisel and shape the inner personality of the human being, apart from widening his knowledge and sharpening his skills. The fist and foremost duty of an educational system is to churn good individuals to the society. Our world, being filled with valuable individuals can become an utopia in itself.

New Education Let us Tell What New Education Quotes

- Sincere pursuit of truth, progress and harmonious organization of the persistent pursuit, and the freedom of a spontaneous, growing and improving order fulfillment by itself.
- Informal teaching, learning fun and thorough dedication, rigorous training, teacher-student relationship widest understanding - these are the new methods of education specifications.
- Constantly fresh youth, a constant thrust to potential new future, and a desire for continuous improvement - these will govern the new educational atmosphere
- A search for life, to pay attention to the overall development of the personality and the highest goal of human life expressed in solidarity - these will be preoccupations of teachers and students in general stereotypes
- In the new education, students will not go to schools and colleges, to listen to lectures, but for a quest to find answers to their questions, in consultation with the teacher when needed,
- The main occupation of teachers will be observing his students, their aptitudes and abilities, which can help them deep sympathy and understanding

Encouraging Factors

- Determined to work hard, regular work, and to develop the habit of discipline
- Solve the short-term or long-term planning, and stick to it strictly (relaxation in this disqualify a student from working)
- Arranging, from time to time, lectures and seminars, some of which are difficult issues to discuss, and to deal quickly and effectively with the short program.
- Issue reports in written format for the work done.
- Clearing the tests
- Other tasks which achieves efficiency, precision, clarity, and mastery. (EFA, 2005)

Conclusion

Good and enjoyable teaching, New Curriculum, Enjoy Teaching, Seven Principles of Good Teaching Practices, Evaluation of Enhancement, The methods of effective of evaluation, Effective Teaching and Motivating Students are the key factors to enjoy teaching. Accounting and Finance Education must be focused to the subjects for which the pedagogy must be adopted using chalk & talk, audio, videos, games, assignments, surprise quizzes, case studies, research projects, group discussions, seminar presentations, guest lectures, workshops, written exams on computer, evaluations through the software, industrial visits, good communication skills, infrastructures of the classroom, digital libraries, laptops with internet connection, monitoring and scrutinizing, transparency, 360 degree evaluation and eagle eyes are very important to promote the stream which help to improve and sustain the subjects also to the real the economy development with proper discipline system in the country.

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